

POST EXPEDITION REPORT

Field Expedition La Réunion Island, France

ATMO-PLASTIC Project

Université
Fédérale
Toulouse
Midi-Pyrénées

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DISCLAIMER

The ideas and opinions expressed in this report are the authors alone. They do not necessarily reflect the opinions or ideas of the funding agencies, employers, or corporate sponsors.

submitted by

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ABSTRACT

This report presents all the samples collected within the framework of the ANR Atmo-Plastic and TJF Carbon Islands projects on the territory of Reunion Island. The objective of these projects is to use the peat bogs of Reunion Island as microplastic traps and thus reveal the history of atmospheric contamination by microplastics in the Indian Ocean over the last fifty years. The surveys will also provide a better understanding of the potential of Reunion's peat bogs as environmental archives and carbon stocks thanks to ongoing carbon-14 dating. The additional samples obtained (water, mosses, lichens) will provide a better understanding of atmospheric contamination on the island.

RESUME

Ce rapport présente l'ensemble des échantillons prélevés dans le cadre des projets ANR Atmo-Plastic et TJF Carbon Islands sur le territoire de l'île de la Réunion. L'objectif de ces projets est d'utiliser les tourbières réunionnaises comme pièges à microplastiques et ainsi révéler l'histoire de la contamination atmosphérique aux microplastiques dans l'Océan Indien ces cinquante dernières années. Les sondages permettront également de mieux connaître le potentiel des tourbières réunionnaises comme archives environnementales et stocks de carbone grâce à des datations carbone-14 en cours. Les échantillons complémentaires obtenus (eaux, mousses, lichens) permettront de mieux connaître la contamination atmosphérique sur l'île.

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Travel, accommodation and logistics

The field expedition started on 10/11/2021 and finished on 20/11/2021.

The French team flew from Toulouse to La Réunion Island (Roland Garros Airport, Saint-Denis) through Paris-Orly Airport. David Beilman flew through continental US, Paris then La Réunion Island.

2 cars (Dacia Duster) were rented through the travel agency of the CNRS: FCM. Cars were picked up at Roland Garros Airport for the entire stay. Helicopter flight to La Réunion was booked at Helilagon.

The French & US team stayed in the village of Plaine des Cafres, Le Tampon municipality - Mavillaô accommodation.

1.1. FUNDING

The field mission was supported by the CNRS through the MITI 4D μ Plast project, the ANR within the project ATMO-PLASTIC and with the Carbon Islands project (Make Our Planet Great Again the

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2. INTRODUCTION

Plastic production has increased exponentially since the 1950s (“Atlas du Plastique | Heinrich Böll Stiftung | Bureau Paris - France,” n.d.). Still, the mismanagement of this product has led to its accumulation in natural environments at a similar rate, as it is estimated that around 80% of the plastic produced ends up in the environment (Geyer et al., 2017). Furthermore, its persistence in the environment allows plastics to interact with weathering processes leading to their fragmentation into small plastic particles. Microplastics (MPs) are plastic particles ranging from 0.1 μm to 5 mm found in all environmental compartments worldwide. Because of their small size, MPs can be easily transported, even through the air. MPs are considered an issue of great concern since they can absorb other pollutants, release lixiviates, carry pathogens, and enter into the organism via ingestion or inhalation (Prata, 2018; Vethaak and Legler, 2021). Concerning natural environment conservation, the transport of stowaway species on the plastic surface could be a major risk for native flora and fauna, especially in isolated habitats (Gregory, 2009).

There are Five Great Plastic Patches in the ocean located within the major ocean gyres (Leal Filho et al., 2021), being the Great Pacific Garbage Patch the most well-known. The Indian Ocean (IO) has remained less explored, although some countries with higher plastic mismanagement are bathed in these waters. Pattiaratchi et al. (2022) identified plastic accumulation in the subtropical gyre (southern IO) that may beach on the coast of the countries in this area, including La Réunion island. Connan et al. (2021) also detected an accumulation zone of plastic southeast of Madagascar, and the abundance of plastic was higher in the direction of La Réunion. From all the plastic collected, the study found that 66% were white items. A fraction of this plastic litter is like to arrive at the coast; however, plastic is exposed to fragmentation, forming MPs which can be released from the ocean into the atmosphere by sea spray (Allen et al., 2020).

La Réunion island is often considered a sister of the Hawaiian island because both show similar volcanic origins, climate, and flora (Le Roux et al., 2014). La Réunion island has the largest area of the intact habitat of the three islands forming the Mascarene archipelago and is considered a biodiversity hotspot. However, those areas are especially vulnerable to biological invasions of alien species, which could decrease the biodiversity on this island (Fenouillas et al., 2021). According to Fenouillas et al., atmospheric transport could be a driver of invasion.

It is well-known that the plastisphere can constitute a new ecological niche for different organisms (micro and macro) (Kießling et al., 2015). However, plastic communities show a reduced taxonomic diversity than natural substrates, although some studies suggest that the loss of microbial diversity has been associated with increased disease transmission (Parthasarathy et al., 2019). According to Goldstein et al. (2014), large plastic shows greater diversity than smaller items.

Mosses and lichens have been largely used as bioindicator organisms as a proxy for atmospheric pollution in industrial, urban, and forested areas (Agnan et al., 2015) especially as a tool for metal pollution biomonitoring. In recent years, mosses and lichens have been used to record microplastic pollution in urban (Stefano et al., 2021) and mountain areas (Allen et al., 2021). *Sphagnum* mosses and *Usnea* lichens are broadly distributed in both hemispheres. *Sphagnum* mosses are helpful for monitoring atmospheric deposition, especially for metal pollution (Kempter et al., 2017). Epiphytic *Usnea* lichens are helpful to record air contamination. Allen et al., (2021) proved that *Sphagnum* peat cores show a greater number of MP in recent years (178 ± 72 particles/ m^2/day) in the Pyrenees mountains. Regarding lichens,

other species have been used to record airborne MP pollution in urban areas, but to our knowledge, not *Usnea* and not in remote environments.

Preliminary studies on microplastics in the atmosphere, in wet deposition (rain and snow) and in soils indicate that the atmosphere can play an important role in the dissemination of microplastics across the globe, including in remote areas such as the Arctic or higher altitude sites. In a recent paper (Allen et al. 2020), we even show that microplastics can be remobilised from the oceans to the atmosphere. The unique situation of Reunion Island and its proximity to the Indian Ocean gyre allow for a better study of this phenomenon of remobilisation of oceanic microplastics into the atmosphere. Furthermore, the location of Reunion Island allows us to study contamination from Africa and Madagascar.

Peat bogs are very interesting environmental archives that mainly receive their input from the atmosphere. We have been able to demonstrate their usefulness in reconstructing atmospheric deposition in the Pyrenees (Allen et al., 2021)

Figure 1: Reconstruction of atmospheric deposition of microplastics in the Pyrenees using a Sphagnum bog

The objective of our sampling is therefore twofold: to study the atmospheric remobilisation of microplastics by the Indian Ocean, today and in the past, using environmental archives such as peat bogs. Indeed, peatlands (and *Sphagnum* mosses) receive almost exclusively atmospheric inputs. We will therefore assess the capacity of Reunion's peatland ecosystems as recorders in time and space (via altitudinal gradients) of micropollutants, including microplastics, but also black carbon and metals.

In order to complete the atmospheric study with sphagnum mosses and peat surveys, we will validate our recent records by using lichens as bioindicators of micropollutants. Their usefulness as bioindicators of micropollutants such as metals has been demonstrated in the past and a recent Italian study showed that lichens could be used as bioindicators of microplastics in the air.

3. LA RÉUNION ISLAND AND SAMPLING SITES

La Réunion Island (France) is located in the western part of the Indian Ocean, approximately 680 km (420 mi) east of the island of Madagascar. Mauritius and Rodrigues, form the Mascarene archipelago, La Réunion, the largest island (2512 km²). It has a population of 868,846 inhabitants (<https://www.insee.fr/fr/accueil>, January 2022), habiting mainly in urban areas (99,6%). La Réunion island

is divided into 24 communes (municipalities) grouped into four districts (*arrondissements*): Saint-Paul, Saint-Denis, Saint-Benoît, and Saint-Pierre (**Fig. 1**), and the capital is Saint-Denis, placed on the coast-line. Tourism and agriculture (sugar export) are the two primary economic resources. More than 80% of the total population and economic activities are concentrated in the coastal lowlands (Strasberg et al., 2005).

La Réunion island presents two shield volcanos, the extinct Piton des Neiges (3.069 m), located in the west-central area of the island, is the highest peak of the island, and it is responsible for the formation of two-thirds of the island (<https://en.reunion.fr/discover/piton-des-neiges-the-heart-and-soul-of-reunion-island/>). The second volcano is The Piton de la Fournaise (2.631 m, SE), considered one of the most active volcanoes in the world since it erupts every nine months on average (<https://en.reunion.fr/discover/piton-de-la-fournaise-the-sacred-furnace/>). The massifs of the Piton des Neiges and the Piton de la Fournaise are separated by the Plaine des Palmistes and the Plaine des Cafres. Due to active erosion processes, La Réunion presents exceptional landscapes characterized by rugged mountains and short torrential rivers. The island of Reunion is characterized by a tropical climate, and it has two seasons: a summer rainfall period from November to April, and a cooler dry season from June to September. Although, precipitation is common due to the trade winds, especially in the southeast area of the island (1500 – 8000 mm), due to the influence of trade wind (dominant ESE direction) (Ah-Peng et al., 2012), while the northwest area presents an average rainfall of 635 mm. The mean annual temperature ranges from 12°C (around 2.000 m) to 24°C (on the coast) (Strasberg et al., 2005 and <https://www.britannica.com/place/Reunion>). However, the rugged topography of the island forms a variety of climatic conditions at a small spatial scale (microclimates), leading to a high habitat diversity (Strasberg et al., 2005). These characteristics have led to consider La Réunion as a hotspot of biodiversity, including its National Park (42% of the surface of the island) as part of the UNESCO World Heritage List (iucn.org).

Regarding its vegetation, the slopes of the volcanoes of La Réunion are heavily forested, probably because the slopes are very steep, which has minimized the human impact on these areas allowing the perseverance of the native forests and their original vegetation (Garot, 2019). Still, the increase in the presence of alien species concerns the conservation status of native habitats (Strasberg et al., 2005). Our sampling was carried out at the end of the dry season (10-15 November 2021) in *Sphagnum*-dominated peatlands at different study sites ranging from 890 to 1.949 m a.s.l (**Fig. 1**) in the Saint-Benoît and Saint-Pierre districts. All sites are included in the National Park of La Reunion area, where native vegetation has remained mostly intact (Fenouillas et al., 2021). Detailed information on each one of these sites can be found in the following sections.

Regarding the home waste produced in La Réunion, a recent study conducted by Lebon et al., (2020) showed that the highest percentage of the waste is composed of putrescible and plastic (40%). The main method for municipal solid waste disposal in La Réunion is landfilling. The island has two open landfills located in the northeast (Saint-Suzanne), and the south (Saint-Pierre), receiving the MSW of more than 300.000 and 500.000 inhabitants, respectively. According to local authorities, both landfills are close to the saturation of their capacity (Lebon et al., 2020).

Field Sampling La Réunion
10 – 20 November 2021

#Point	Location
1	Piton Tortue (Le Tampon, REU)
2	Piton Tortue (Le Tampon, REU)
3	Pandanaies (Plaine des palmistes)
4	Plateau de thym (Forêt de Bébour, Saint-Benoit, REU)
5	GR-R1 Cap Anglais (Saint-Benoit, REU)
6	Savane cimetièrre (Sainte-Rose, REU)

<https://www.mapprc.com/counties/arrondissements-of-reunion/>

Figure 1. List of the sampling sites and their locations in La Réunion. The port, airports and landfills are also indicated. The trade wind is dominant in the ESE direction.

3.1. Point 1: Piton Tortue (Le Tampon, Saint-Pierre)

The first point (1739 m) is placed in the Forêt Domaniale de la Plaine des Cafres. The point is on the south side of a hill placed in the limit of agricultural lands, 1 km away from Piton Tortue (south direction). The point is inside a hiking area, close to the trail Sentier Mollaret. The site presents a slight slope, and due to the presence of tall shrubs, point 1 is a closed wet area. The vegetation is formed by 90-95% of tall shrubs, being *Erica reunionensis* the dominant species, reaching a height of 4-5 m. The undergrowth is dominated by *Sphagnum* sp. (pending species identification) and the presence of two other bryophytes (*Hymenophyllum inaequalis* and unidentified spp.). We took samples of *Sphagnum* and *Usnea* sp., which grow in the branches of *E. reunionensis*.

Type of vegetation: tree heather formations (Cheke and Hume, 2010) of *E. reunionensis*

Habitat: mountain heather thicket (Strasberg et al., 2005)

Figure 2. Location of point 1, pictures from the surrounding area..

3.2. Point 2: Piton Tortue (Le Tampon, Saint-Pierre)

The second point (1678 m) is also placed in the Forêt Domaniale de la Plaine des Cafres. The point is approximately 2 km away from Piton Tortue (north-east direction). It is a wet flat area placed at 50 m from the hiking trail Setier Forestier de Bébou, covered by >60 % of tall shrubs of *E. reunionensis* (4-5 m of height), forming a dense canopy. The undergrowth is covered by two species of *Sphagnum* (pending identification). We took samples of both *Sphagnum* species. We collected some thalis of *Usnea* sp. from the branches of *E. reunionensis*, but this time the lichens were placed > 2 m from the ground, hampering their collection.

Type of vegetation: tree heather formations (Cheke & Hume, 2010) of *E. reunionensis*

Habitat: mountain heather thicket (Strasberg et al., 2005)

Figure 3. Location of point 2, pictures from the surrounding area, and detail of the two patches of *Sphagnum*.

3.3. Point 3: Pandanaies (La Plaine-des-Palmistes, Saint-Benoît)

Pandanaies site (890 m) is a flat mire located on the outskirts of La Plaine-des-Palmistes, a small village of 6.626 inhabitants (80/km²). This jungle is dominated by *Pandanus montanus* and *E. reunionensis*. The undergrowth was dominated by gramineous, ferns, and bryophytes, such as *Sphagnum* sp and *Lycopodiella* sp. Although it is a sunny area, the substrate was wet because the vegetation is dense. We took samples of *Sphagnum* sp., but *Usnea* sp. thalis were scarce and small.

Type of vegetation: wet forest (Cheke & Hume, 2010)

Habitat: mountain *Pandanus* wet thicket (Strasberg et al., 2005)

Figure 4. Location of point 3, pictures from the surrounding area, and vegetation..

3.4. **Point 4: Plateau de thym (Forêt de Bébour, Saint-Benoît)**

The Plateau de thym site (1536 m) is located in the Forêt de Bébour. The site is a *Sphagnum*-dominated peatland located in the centre of the island, between The Piton des Neiges and La Plaine-des-Palmistes,. It is a flat area, and the dominant shrub vegetation is *E. galioides* and *E. reunionensis* (max. 2 m). The undergrowth presents large patches of *Sphagnum* sp., and some spots with *Cladonia* sp. The peatland is a sunny and open area with <10% canopy cover. During the sampling, we found no water in the pond where we collected the samples. Although, the deepest substrate was wet. The site is a known hiking area, and we observed remains of plastic litter in the surrounding area of our sampling point. At this site, we collected several thalys of *Usnea* lichen and five samples of *Sphagnum* surface samples.

Type of vegetation: subtropical acacia-dominated montane rainforest (Cheke & Hume, 2010)

Habitat: mountain windward rainforest (Strasberg et al., 2005)

Figure 5. Location of point 4, pictures from the landscape and vegetation..

3.5. **Point 5: GR-R1 Cap Anglais (Saint-Benoît)**

The fifth sampling point (1949 m) was approximately 200 m from the GR1 trail. Following the GR1 trail in the direction to the Piton des Neiges, the study site is placed on the southeast side of the ridge of the Cirque de Salazie, approximately in the centre part of the island. The site is a *Sphagnum*-dominated peatland surrounded by a forest formation of *E. reunionensis* (4-5 m). The peatland is a sunny flat area without trees, except for a scarce *E. reunionensis* (<2 m), and presents small ponds (some of them dried during the time of the sampling). The ground is covered by *Sphagnum* sp., with a few thalys of *Cladonia* sp., grass and small shrubs of *E. reunionensis*.

Type of vegetation: subtropical montane mixed evergreen subtropical rainforest (Cheke & Hume, 2010)

Habitat: mountain windward rainforest (Strasberg et al., 2005)

Figure 6. Location of point 5, pictures from the landscape and vegetation, and pictures of *Sphagnum* sp. and *Usnea* sp. individuals.

3.6. Point 6: Savane cimetière (Sainte-Rose, Saint-Benoît)

The last point is categorized as subalpine shrubland (Strasberg et al., 2015), called Savane Cimentière (1873 m), and is located on the east of the island, approximately 5 km northwest direction from Piton de la Fournaise, the active volcano. The vegetation is dominated by small shrubs of *E. reunionensis* and grass.

Type of vegetation: subtropical upper montane temperate heaths (Cheke & Hume, 2010)

Habitat: subalpine shrubland (Strasberg et al., 2005)

Figure 7. Location of point 6, pictures from the landscape and vegetation.

3.7. Point 7: Plaine des fougères (Saint-Denis)

Type of vegetation: montane mixed vegetation subtropical rainforest (Cheke & Hume, 2010)

Habitat: mountain windward forest (Strasberg et al., 2005)

4. SAMPLING METHODS

4.1. Sphagnum collection

Figure 1: conceptual sketch to show how Sphagnum mosses can intercept particulate pollutants

We collected surface *Sphagnum* using a stainless-steel ring (\varnothing 8 cm x 4.5 cm) and a ceramic knife. All field material was rinsed with filtered water (or peat water) before use and between sites. We collected five samples per site to have a general representation of each site. Whenever possible, we collected five *Sphagnum* samples in different cardinal directions (3-5 m) from the central point where we collected a peat core. Samples were collected in flat areas, and after collection, they were wrapped in an aluminium foil pocket and labelled. **Figure 8** shows the collection method followed in each case.

Figure 8. Sampling strategy followed in each site for *Sphagnum* and lichen collection.

4.2. Lichen collection

Individual sampling was done by collecting lichen from the thalli and carefully removing wood remains. Lichens were handpicked from the branches of 3-5 trees around the sampling area 0.5-2 m above the ground level. After collection, lichens from the same site were wrapped in one aluminium foil pocket and labelled. If *Usnea* was not present or we detected different specie (ex. *Cladonia* sp.)s, individuals were placed in different aluminium pockets. Currently, there is no recent key of determination to identify the species of the genus *Usnea* of La Réunion island. For this reason, we are collaborating with botanists¹ to develop a determination key which will allow identifying the *Usnea* species from La Réunion.

4.3. Peat Core collection

Peat cores were taken with a box corer (homemade - Univ. Gent) for the first metre of smooth peat and moss. Deeper samples were taken with a Belarusian peat corer (Eijkelkamp). We also used a soil profile corer (Eijkelkamp). Samples were then either cut in the field to avoid plastic contamination and stored frozen in aluminium foil, or cores were wrapped in thick plastic film and stored in cardboard and wooden boxes.

Figure 2: Soil profile corer

¹ Dr Philippe Clerc (Department of Culture and Digital Transition, Ville de Genève)

4.4. Seawater collection

To get an overview of the plastic composition of the coastal waters around the island of La Réunion, we collected seawater samples using a home-made device. After collecting the water using a titanium bucket, we pre-filtered the seawater through a cascade filter device using cleaned nylon filters of 100 and 50 μm , respectively, and then filtered the final sample using a PTFE-Teflon membrane filter. All equipment was either pre-cleaned in the laboratory or pre-cleaned with seawater at each site.

4.5. Aerosol collection

Aerosol filters were collected using an air pump with a 0.45 μm Teflon filter located in the Mavilao house, le Tampon and at la Station de recherche sur les espaces naturels et anthropisés du Sud de la Réunion à St Philippe.

Figure 3: aerosol collection setting

5. LIST OF SAMPLES

5.1. 5.1. Moss and lichens

Table 1. List of samples and details of each sampling site. *Abbreviations: REU refers to “La Réunion”*

Point	Coordinates (X)	Coordinates (Y)	Altitude (m)	Date (yyyy/mm/dd)	Location	Sample ID
1	21°09'39"S	55°33'21.9"E	1739	20211112	Piton Tortue (Le Tampon, REU)	REU_1a
						REU_1b
						REU_1c
						REU_1d
						REU_1e
						REU_1_usnea
2	21°08'43.7"S	55°34'14.3"E	1678	20211112	Piton Tortue (Le Tampon, REU)	REU_2a
						REU_2b
						REU_2c
						REU_2d
						REU_2e
						REU_2extra
REU_2_usnea						
3	21°07'01.5"S	55°38'55.4"E	890	20211113	Pandanaies (Plaine des palmists, REU)	REU_3a
						REU_3b
						REU_3c
						REU_3d
						REU_3e
						REU_3_lichens
4	21°05'51.8"S	55°32'51.6"E	1536	20211113	Plateau de thym (Foret de Bébou, Saint-Benoit, REU)	REU_4a
						REU_4b
						REU_4c
						REU_4d
						REU_4e
						REU_4_lichens
5	21°05'17"S	55°31'27"E	1949	20211114	GR-R1 Cap Anglais (Saint-Benoit, REU)	REU_5a
						REU_5b
						REU_5c
						REU_5d
						REU_5e
						REU_5f
						REU_5g
						REU_5h
						REU_5_usnea
REU_5_lichen						
6	21°11'41"S	55°42'33"E	1873	20211115	Savane cimetièrè (Sainte-Rose, REU)	REU_6a
						REU_6b
						REU_6c
						REU_6d
						REU_5e

5.2. Peat cores

Piton Bébour/ Plaine des Cafres forest: Sphagnum accumulation under forest // Accumulation de Sphaignes “fourrées” sous forêt

4 short cores (REU 1-A; REU 1-B; REU 2-A; REU 2-B) were sampled using a soil corer from Eijkelkamp. The cores were subsampled on the field.

**Plaine des Palmistes- *Sphagnum* accumulation on swampy *Pandanus* groves
Accumulation de Sphaignes et tourbes sous «aulnaies » à *Pandanus***

2 cores (REU-3A, REU-3B) using the box corer were taken. Core A was subsampled on the field every 2cm.

Note from macrofossil extraction: at 58cm depth, *Sphagnum* moss occurrence

**Mare au thym/ Belouve-Bebour- *Sphagnum* Peat bog
Haut Marais à *Sphaignes***

2 cores (REU 4A, REU 4B) were taken using a box corer and we then used a Ejkelpkamp Russian core to take 50cm cores to 275 depth when a clay layer was reached.

REU 4A box core description:

Sphagnum layer to 20cm

Acrotelm to 28cm

Brown dense peat to 36cm

Transition 36-42cm

Organic silty mud 42-75cm

REU 4A russian cores to 275cm depth (75-125; 125-175; 175-225; 225-275)

REU 4B overlap core (100-150; 150-200)

Note from macrofossil extraction for radiocarbon: alternating peaty and sedimentary layers after 50 cm depth but at 150cm depth, clear layer of Sphagnum peat accumulation

Cap Anglais *Sphagnum* bog on seasonal wetlands// Buttes à Sphaignes sur mares saisonnières

2 short cores (REU5A, REU5B) were extracted from *Sphagnum* hummocks using the box corer. This ecosystem is peculiar with hummocks of sphagnum moss well present on a wetland but without peat accumulation.

REU 5A description

0-5cm: loose sphagnum

5-20cm: compact dense sphagnum

20-30cm: dark brown peat

30-48cm: organic mud

REU 5B description:

0-10cm: fluffy fresh sphagnum

10-30: increasing degrading sphagnum

30-42: dark decomposed peat-catotelm

42-56cm: organic mud

REU 5C description:

0-14cm loose recent sphagnum

14-24cm: compacted sphagnum

24-31cm: peat

31-60cm: organic mud

Savane cimetière *Sphagnum* blanket bog//Tourbière de couverture à Sphaignes

REU 6A description

0-1 living sphagnum

1-14cm acrotelm-well preserved sphagnum

14-100cm well decomposed dark brown peat

REU 6A 100-150cm: russian complementary peat core

REU6B description

0-1cm living sphagnum

1-14cm: Acrotelm-fluffy poor decomposed sphagnum

14-80cm: dark brown organic mud

In REU6B, at 52cm cm depth, there is an *ash layer*.

REU6C:

0-4 living mosses including Sphagnum and Dicranoloma

14-15: decomposed moss

15-75: decomposed peat

5.3. Seawater

#	Point	Location	Target MP size (μm)	Volume of sample (L)
1	SW1	Saint-Benoit	>100 μm	51
			50 - 100 μm	51
			0.45 - 50 μm	5
2	SW2	Anse-des-Cascades	>100 μm	90
			50 - 100 μm	90
			0.45 - 50 μm	5
3	SW3	Saint-Philippe	>100 μm	135
			50 - 100 μm	135
			0.45 - 50 μm	5
4	SW4	Grand-Anse	>100 μm	120
			50 - 100 μm	120
			0.45 - 50 μm	5
5	SW5	Harbour of Saint Pierre	>100 μm	90
			50 - 100 μm	90
			0.45 - 50 μm	5
6	SW6	Étang Sale des Boins	>100 μm	114
			50 - 100 μm	114
			0.45 - 50 μm	5
7	SW7	Saint-Leu	>100 μm	84
			50 - 100 μm	84
			0.45 - 50 μm	5
8	SW8	Boucan Canot	>100 μm	99
			50 - 100 μm	99
			0.45 - 50 μm	5

5.4. 5.4. Aerosols

Filters used were 0.45 μm 47mm PVDF (teflon) filters in PFA (teflon) filter packs, pumped for 4 days at about 10 LPM

Mavilao, Bourg Murat - La Plaine des Cafres, -21.195 S, 55.578 E, 10m asl

- Sample 1 Start, 11/11/2021, 14h, 49780.265 m³- Stop, 16/11/2021, 9h, 49848.731 m³
- Sample 2 Start, 16/11/2021, 9h, 49848.731 m³ - Stop, 20/11/2021, 9h, 49907.329 m³

Saint Philippe field station, -21.362 S, 55.764 E,

- Sample 1 Start, 12/11/2021, 14h, 33534.200 m³- Stop, 16/11/2021, 14h, 33606.064 m³
- Sample 2 Start, 16/11/2021, 14h, 33606.064 m³- Stop, 19/11/2021, 10h, 33651.131 m³

5.5. other prospected sites for peat coring

Figure 4: Plaine des Fougères (Sphagnum present – see sampled mosses) but no peat

Figure 5: Sentier Mollaret:

Figure 6: Along the GR R1

6. CONCLUSIONS & PERSPECTIVES

The field trip was a decisive success, with peat cores, moss and lichen samples collected from a variety of sites across the island of Réunion. Complementary samples (aerosols and seawater) were also collected. The peat samples are currently being dated using radiocarbon techniques. 16 samples from REU4, REU5 and REU6 were sent to the radiocarbon facilities in Univ. Gliwice and Artemis Natioanl facility for age dating. Peat samples have been analysed for low resolution geochemistry using portable XRF and will be further analysed for geochemistry using ICP-MS. Recent peat layers are now being analysed for microplastic particles using Raman microscopy. Similar studies are being carried out on lichen and moss samples.

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